

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TITANIUM TETRABROMIDE. PART III

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The amino derivatives of titanous bromide have been prepared by the action of titanium tetrabromide on some aliphatic amines and heterocyclic bases, and their properties studied.

Rosenheim and Schütte (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 26, 239) had studied the action of titanous acid in alcoholic hydrobromic acid on pyridine hydrobromide and isolated pyridinobromotitanous acid, $(C_5H_5N)_2 \cdot H_2TiBr_6$. In continuation of our earlier work (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 838; 1957, 34, 452), the present investigation has been carried out with a view to studying the action of anhydrous titanous bromide on some aliphatic amines and heterocyclic bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines and heterocyclic bases used were of Merck's or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared as before (*loc. cit.*). Sodium hypobromite, used in the potentiometric studies for the estimation of amines and heterocyclic bases, was prepared according to the method described by Kolthoff ("*Volumetric Analysis*", 1929, Vol. II, p. 468).

The compounds were prepared and analysed according to the methods described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and their properties studied. In all the compounds except *tetrakis- α -picolino-*, *tetrakis-pyridino-* and *bis-nicotino-titanous bromides*, the amine and heterocyclic base were also estimated by potentiometric method and the percentage of nitrogen in the compounds calculated. Two sets of titrations were carried out in each case. The results recorded in Table I are the average of the two values.

Estimation of Amine and Heterocyclic Base by Potentiometric Method.—The compound ($\approx 0.25-1.4$ g.) was weighed out accurately, dissolved in 2*N*- H_2SO_4 and made feebly alkaline with NaOH solution. It was then filtered and the residue (titanium hydroxide) washed well with water. The filtrate and the washings were collected and the volume made up to 250 c.c. An aliquot portion of the solution was taken in a beaker and titrated against a standard solution of sodium hypobromite (0.08*N*) at the room temperature. When sodium hypobromite is added to the feebly alkaline solution of the compound, a gradual change in potential occurs, but near the equivalence point there is an abrupt change in potential (due to a slight excess of the reagent). This change in potential is very sharp in the case of *tetrakis-dimethylamino-*, *tetrakis-diethylamino-*, *tetrakis-piperidino-* and *bis-piperazino-titanous bromides*, as shown in Fig. 1, but not so marked in the case of *tetrakis-n-butylamino-*, *bis-ethylenediamino-* and *tetrakis-trimethylamino-titanous bromides*. Similar titrations were carried out with *bis-nicotino-*, *tetrakis- α -picolino-* and *tetrakis-pyridino-titanous bromides* under identical conditions, but no definite conclusions could be drawn from the observations.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

As the amines and the heterocyclic bases examined form N-mono, di- or tri-bromo derivatives and some of them even perbromides (Sahasrabudhey *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 652), blank experiments have been carried out by titrating the pure amine or heterocyclic base under identical conditions, but only the curves for diethylamine and piperidine (Fig. 1, curves I & II) are shown.

Sodium hypobromite in feebly alkaline medium reacts with aliphatic amines forming N-mono or dibromo derivatives with primary amines, depending upon the quantity of hypobromite used and only N-monobromo derivative with secondary amines. The reactions in general may be represented in the case of a primary amine as :

and in the case of a secondary amine as :

However, ethylenediamine forms N-tetrabromoethylenediamine

The quantity of hypobromite consumed in the case of trimethylamine indicates the formation of N-dibromo derivative and may be represented as :

This derivative was also isolated in dilute alkaline medium by Sahasrabudhey *et al.* (*loc.cit.*).

The reactions with heterocyclic bases are similar to those with secondary amines. The bromo derivatives formed at the equivalence point are

with piperidine and piperazine respectively.

The curves III-IV in Fig. 1 and VII-IX in Fig. 2 refer to the estimation of the amine in *tetrakis*-dimethylamino-, *tetrakis*-diethylamino-, *tetrakis*-piperidino-, *bis*-piperazino-, *tetrakis*-*n*-butylamino-, *bis*-ethylenediamino- and *tetrakis*-trimethylamino-titanic bromides respectively.

TABLE I
(T. B. denotes titanio bromide).

Compound.	Compound.	Weight of the		% Nitrogen.
		Amine (calc.).	Amine (found from the curves).	
Diethylamine	0.4178 g.	0.5178 g.	0.5201 g.	19.27
Piperidine	0.3454	0.3454	0.3468	16.54
<i>tetrakis</i> -Dimethylamino-T.B.	0.7740	0.2542	0.2538	10.20
" diethylamino T.B.	0.7276	0.3219	0.3211	8.47
" piperidino-T.B.	1.3918	0.6684	0.6694	7.93
<i>bis</i> -Piperazino-T.B.	0.5170	0.1647	0.1651	10.40
<i>tetrakis</i> - <i>n</i> -Butylamino-T.B.	0.4676	0.2069	0.2073	8.50
<i>bis</i> -Ethylenediamino-T.B.	0.2388	0.0587	0.0588	11.50
<i>tetrakis</i> -Trimethylamino-T.B.	0.4638	0.1812	0.1817	9.30

TABLE II

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with aliphatic amines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	<i>tetrakis</i> - <i>n</i> -Butylamino-T.B. [Ti (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	...	7.24	7.27	48.32	48.48	8.35	8.48
Ethylenediamine	<i>bis</i> -Ethylenediamino-T.B. $\left[\text{Ti} \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2 \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2 \end{array} \right)_2 \right] \text{Br}_4$	Light yellow	330°	9.79	9.84	65.43	65.57	11.29	11.48
Dimethylamine	<i>tetrakis</i> -Dimethylamino-T.B. [Ti {(CH ₃) ₂ NH ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Greyish white	295°	8.78	8.76	58.45	58.39	10.14	10.32
Diethylamine	<i>tetrakis</i> -Diethylamino-T.B. [Ti {(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NH ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Yellowish white	300°	7.26	7.27	48.35	48.48	8.42	8.48
Nicotine	<i>bis</i> -Nicotino-T.B. [Ti (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂) ₂]Br ₄	Reddish orange	136°	6.90	6.94	46.12	46.24	8.04	8.09
Trimethylamine	<i>tetrakis</i> -Trimethylamino-T.B. [Ti {(CH ₃) ₃ N} ₄]Br ₄	White with a yellow shade	288°	7.98	7.95	52.85	52.98	9.13	9.27

TABLE III

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with heterocyclic bases.

Heterocyclic base.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Piperidine	<i>tetrakis</i> -Piperidino-T.B. [Ti(C ₅ H ₁₁ N) ₄]Br ₄	Yellow-white	304°	6.74	6.78	45.12	45.20	7.82	7.91
Pyridine	<i>tetrakis</i> -Pyridino-T.B. [Ti(C ₅ H ₅ N) ₄]Br ₄	White	167°	7.03	7.02	46.56	46.78	8.05	8.19
<i>α</i> -Picoline	<i>tetrakis-α</i> -picolino-T.B. [Ti(C ₆ H ₇ N) ₄]Br ₄	Orange	132°	6.45	6.49	43.16	43.24	7.40	7.57
Piperazine	<i>bis</i> -Piperazino-T.B. [Ti(C ₄ H ₁₀ N ₂) ₂]Br ₄	White	350°	8.82	8.89	59.19	59.26	10.12	10.37

Properties of the Compounds.—The compounds formed with titanium tetrabromide and aliphatic amines or heterocyclic bases are similar to those formed with the aromatic amines. These are almost insoluble in absolute alcohol, benzene, CCl₄, CHCl₃, acetone and petroleum ether, but readily soluble in cold dilute mineral acids. Hydrolysis of the compounds starts when in contact with water, but complete hydrolysis takes place only on boiling. Hydrolysis is facilitated by Na₂CO₃ or NaOH, precipitating titanium hydroxide :

where 'A' represents the amine or heterocyclic base.

When these are heated alone, a compound separates out, which is soluble in water, acidic and gives the test for Br⁻ and -NH₂, = NH and : N in the case of primary, secondary and tertiary amines respectively and for Br⁻, = NH and : N in the case of heterocyclic bases. On heating with sodalime the corresponding amine or heterocyclic base separates out. These derivatives are fairly stable except *tetrakis-α*-picolinotitanic bromide, which is very hygroscopic and begins to hydrolyse when exposed to atmosphere, though it is stable when kept in perfectly dry atmosphere or in vacuum.

The structures of these compounds appear to be similar to those formed with amines as shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

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